

Employee Intrinsic Motivation and The Attainment of the Organisation Goals: A Case of Private University in Malawi

**Author(s), ANGELA EWHONNE NWAOMAH, PHD
AND
ROSE MANDALA TSUKANI, MBA**

Abstract:

Employee motivation is a very important subject as far as the achievement of organisation goals in universities is concerned. This has been recognised by some studies on staff motivation in Malawi and even abroad. Nevertheless, not much has been done on the factors that affected the achievement of organisation goals. Therefore, this study examined the effect of intrinsic motivation factors on the achievement of organisation goals at Malawi Adventist University.

A causal type of study design conducted in one month was used for the study. The university population was two hundred forty-one employees whose employment status was permanent and contract, teaching and non-teaching excluding those on wages. To ensure that all employees were represented, employees were randomly selected for the study. Krejcie and Morgan pre-calculated sample size table was used to select a sample of 181 employees from the population. Data was collected with a self-structured questionnaire validated with Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of .579 on intrinsic motivation factors and .690 on the attainment of organisation goals. A total of 146 copies of the questionnaire were validly completed and returned representing 81% response rate. Descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple regression analyses were used to analyse the data.

The results revealed that at the 0.05 level of significance, intrinsic motivation factors such as nature of work and responsibility significantly and positively affected the achievement of organisation goals at Malawi Adventist University as evidenced by the p-values of (.180, 1.961 and .052) and (.225, 2.574 and .011).

The study concluded that intrinsic motivation factors of work life balance, nature of work, equity and fairness, responsibility and recognition are important towards achieving organisation goals even though their importance were not at equal proportion. Therefore, recommendation was made to help the management to optimize the attainment of organisation goals at Malawi Adventist University.

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About Author

Author(s), 1: Associate Professor/University Registrar
Adventist University of Africa,
Private Bag Mbagathi 00503, Nairobi, Kenya.

Corresponding Author: E-mail: nwaomaha@aua.ac.ke
2: Business Manager
Malamulo Secondary School,
P.O Box 33, Makwasa, Malawi.
E-mail: tsukanir@malamulosec.adventist.org

(Corresponding Author) Email:

INTRODUCTION

Many organisations face the problem of staff motivation at the work place. This is because most managers are not able to inspire employees' motivation at work (Heathfield, 2016). Motivating employees to perform to their maximum potential is partly the responsibility of managers in an organisation to achieve organisational goals. Employees have high expectations of how they want to be treated at work. They do not just want a job that is secure and well-paying but a job that gives them high levels of job satisfaction (Lipman, 2013). Unlike physical assets employees have their own individual needs which must be met and habits which must be managed well to contribute to organisation growth and development. The organisation success or failure is determined by the presence and the contributions of the employees in collaboration with the organisation goals (Osabiya, 2015).

Mullins (2009) states that motivation is concerned with why people act in a certain way towards achieving organisation goals and objectives. Accordingly, motivation is the attribute and the influence that induces employees either to act or not to act in the organisation. Thus, the employees' positive actions come from the satisfaction while negative actions come from dissatisfaction from their organisation.

It is vital for managers to take part to care for their employees to ensure high levels of production and organisations' goal achievement.

Statement of the Problem

Managers in today's organisations need employees who can exert the needed effort to achieve organisation's goals. However, the possibility of achieving organisation goals depends on employees' zeal to work and how management provides a good motivational system that triggers high performance. Hence, the success and the achievement of any organisational goals depend on the ability and willingness of employees to fulfil their work obligation beyond expectation and proper motivation is the key to building such a will. The Malawi Adventist University seems to be facing low employee morale and employees loath to provide their service wholeheartedly hence they lack passion and zeal to work for the institution and willingness to go an extra mile with their respective work and achieve the organisations' goals. This calls for a research to find out why there was such behaviour at Malawi Adventist University. The study therefore, sought to examine the effect of employees' motivation on the attainment of organisation goals at Malawi Adventist University.

Based on the above statement problems, this research question was raised to guide the study.

- What are the intrinsic motivation factors that are important to employees in their achievement of organisation goals at Malawi Adventist University?

The study was piloted by this null research hypothesis:

- **Ho1:** Intrinsic motivation factors does not significantly affect the achievement of organisational goals at Malawi Adventist University.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of motivation in the workplace is defined in various ways. Colquitt (2013) and Robbins (2010) define motivation as the set of energetic forces that originates both from within and outside an employee. This energetic force initiates work-related effort. It also determines the work's direction, intensity, and persistence. However, Hossain (2012) defined motivation as the driving force originating from within the person that stimulates the employee to act with a target to fulfil a required organisation's need and expectation.

Richard (2014) as cited by Denhardt *et al.* (2008) agrees with Hossain (2012) that motivation is an internal state that causes people to behave in a particular way to accomplish particular goals and purposes. Seleemi (2009) also describes motivation as drives or impulses within an individual that prompts employees into action. He observed that these motives are expressions of personal needs and wants hence they are personal and internal. Mullins (2009) concurs Seleemi (2009) that motivation is personal and very complex because employees have a variety of changing and conflicting needs and expectations which managers attempt to satisfy. While Hossain (2012), Seleemi (2009) and Richard (2014) view motivation as the driving force originating from the inside, Lai (2011) and Guay (2010) see motivation as the "reason underlying behaviour". In this view, Mullins (2009) states that motivation is concerned with why people act in a certain way towards achieving organisation goals and objectives. Accordingly, motivation is the attribute and the influence that induces employees either to act or not to act in the organisation. Thus, the employees' positive actions come from the satisfaction while negative actions come from dissatisfaction from their organization. Even though these authors have different views on the concept of motivation, all of them have one thing in common: the "drive" and the "behaviour" that influences action.

Intrinsic motivation is doing something because it is inherently interesting or enjoyable to an employee (Ryan and Deci 2000). Lai (2011) concurs with Ryan and Deci (2000) that intrinsic motivation is emanated from the employees' enjoyment and the inclusion of the employees' pleasure. Nevertheless, there are so many factors of employees' motivation as pointed by different authors, but for the sake of this study, six intrinsic factors will be referred to. These Intrinsic motivation factors are work life balance, nature of work, well being, equity and fairness, responsibility and recognition. These selected motivating factors will be attributed to Malawi Adventist University employees.

Work-life Balance as a Factor of motivation

Work life balance is a very broad phenomenon that has wide definitions (Balance, n.d). He defined it as the extent to which an individual is equally engaged in and equally satisfied with his or her work role and family role. Work life balance can be in many forms. Boulder (2012) believes that providing alternate work schedules (flex schedules) to employees give a powerful tool for management to fulfil business needs and accommodate a changing workforce for a better work-life balance.

On the other hand, Rife (2015) states “work-life balance policies frequently include benefits such as flexible work hours, child-and elder-care provisions, paid maternity leave, adoption assistance, leave/time off, education assistance, health assistance, and housing assistance p.6. Singh (2014) argues that balancing of work demands and family life are very essential and are associated with the mental and the physical health of the employees. However, according to Rife (2015) research clearly shows that regardless of what the organization promotes, direct supervisors or managers greatly influence the work-life balance of their subordinates. Manager’s who focus on the desired work product, rather than requiring “face time” or logging overtime hours, can better enable their employees to balance work and life demands.

Where work and personal life is balanced and wisely managed, employees in an organisation enjoy both personal life and work demands (Singh, 2013). This enables employees to avoid disturbing working hours with personal responsibilities. Shankar (2014) avers better quality work life lead to increased employee morale. Consequently, this limits and reduces costs for non-work-related absenteeism due to personal life issues.

Nature of Work as a Factor of Motivation

Work itself can also be one of the factors of motivation to employees in the organisation (Colquitt, 2013). Thus, employees work hard when they enjoy their work. This is because enjoyment intrinsically provides them job satisfaction. Hence, the employees appreciate their job and work hard passionately. In turn, the demands of the job and the goals of the organization are achieved effectively. In addition, Hackman (1967) observes that motivation through work require a person engagement in challenging activities that stretches their skills, abilities and meaning to the employee. Therefore, they put more effort to accomplish the task as they strive to achieve the organizational goals.

Moreover, Burton (2012) and Hossain (2012) assert that providing a clear and understandable job description can motivate employees to work since they are aware of what is expected of them in relation to their job description. Further, Ganta (2014) states that job enrichment, job enlargement and job rotation are important factors that give employees a

sense of courage and ownership of the job. The link between employee motivation and performance is quite obvious.

With that in mind, managers need to find creative ways in which to consistently keep their employees motivated as much as possible. Motivation is very important for every company to improve the employee performance and productivity of the organisation.

Attention to Individual Matters (Well being) as Factor of Motivation

While teamwork is an important element of company success in the organisation, nothing can beat individual attention when it comes to individual motivation (Demers, 2006). If managers give employees more attention to their personal matters, employees would feel motivated and they would perceive their managers as considerate.

This is done through management regular visiting employees in their work stations to find out how they are progressing. When they are stuck and their challenges seem daunting, management can give the necessary support and encouragement rather than reproof. According to Demers (2015), employees who experience care, love and the consideration from their managers on individual aspiration and problems, whether at home or at work, will feel that they are part of the family hence motivation to perform to the fullest. Additionally, management can further explain how individual welfare challenges can affect negatively the progress of the organization and how in turn the challenges of the organization can affect the employee's individual well-being. Further, Hossain (2012) posits that when employees realize that they are being treated as human beings they tend to be loyal to management hence they work hard and achieve organisation goals without being pushed.

Wollenberg (2014) articulates that it is easy to attract and retain employees' talent in an organisation when the organisation has built a good reputation for taking good care of its workforce. Just by giving out a fruit to employees, according to Wollenberg (2014), would mean a lot and this will show that managers care for their employee's health (Perrin, n.d). For instance, laughing in the office can change an employee well being (Smedley, 2013). He declares a great office is an office filled with laughter whereby the work can be rewarding and challenging but if there is no humour in an employees' day to day life, his or her job becomes a grind. Hence, a need for a close consideration of employee's well being as a source of motivation

Equity and Fairness as a Factor of Motivation

Equity is the desire of every employee whether junior or senior in the organisation. Adebayo (2005) posits that equity theory is one other model that is applicable in understanding workplace fairness. He pronounces that the theory is concerned with how individuals evaluate and react to differences in treatment at the workplace. Equity is how fairly

and equally an employee is treated in comparison with others within or without the organisation (Samson, 2009). Adebayo (2005) states that employees tend to compare their inputs that include qualities and characteristics that person poses such as age, seniority, education, effort and skills with what he/she receive.

Negatively, this may relate to the discrepancies in the rewards they get at the end of the month in relation to what they have put in the organisation (Adebayo, 2005). Employees feel robbed when they compare their packages with others who contribute less to the organization even with less qualifications as well. Thus, they develop negative attitude towards managers since they believe that they are not fairly treated in their organisation, hence de motivation.

Therefore, equity in the organisation can be considered a motivator or a de-motivator to the employee. Mejia (2008) affirms this by observing that an employee in an organisation has beliefs about fairness. He asserts that what is fair to one employee may not be fair to another. While there is a sense of unfairness in the organisation that might not be a formal grievance or a sufficient cause to look for fresh pastures, it can be fatal to employee's performance (Smedley, 2013). Consequently, lack of fairness affects the motivation, the attitudes, and the behaviours of employees towards work; hence, low performance. Al-zawahreh (2012) avers that the "an unfair system is one in which has a lack of predictability, such that arbitrary decisions are made and employees fear victimization. Managers should be aware of the benefits of behaving toward subordinates in a manner perceived as fair. Managers should be concerned with how they treat their employees because employee's perceptions of that treatment could affect the level of citizenship behaviour" p. 22 as well as productivity.

Responsibility as a Factor of Employee Motivation

Although work environment and working conditions are the crucial factors of employee motivation, responsibility delegation must also be included in the working conditions of the organisation. This is where top management does not limit the employees' task but creating a sense of responsibility in employees (Raziq, 2015). If managers do not trust that their employees can manage the work, definitely they would not pass on their responsibility. This does not enhance the confidence and motivation of employees (Lavinsky, 2012). A confident employee works beyond the managers' expectation due to his or her excitement in achieving the organisation goals.

Further, responsible and motivated employees own the organisation as such they take the challenges and the success of their organisation as their own. This is possible if employees are satisfied and motivated (Clerks, 2017 and Boulder, 2012). According to Riley (2005), an employee sense of responsibility encourages them to feel that their contributions are valuable

for the success of the organisation. In order to achieve the maximum, managers must at times assign jobs and responsibilities to employees to induce their level of motivation to perform.

Employee Recognition as a Factor of Motivation

Every employee in an organisation desire to be acknowledged for the contribution he/she is making to the organisation. Hossain (2012) as cited in Glanz (2002) states that appreciation is one of the top desires of employees which motivates and keep them productive in the workplace. This enhances the employees' morale to work hard, to think better for themselves and sharpen their abilities to achieve organisation goals (Hossain, 2012). This is affirmed by Safiullah (2015) as cited in Lai (2009) who points out that recognized employees work efficiently by extending much of their efforts, participating in work related issues and hence low rate of absenteeism.

Abraham Maslow's theory of 1943 ranked employee recognition as an employee's esteem factor while in 1959 Herzberg two factor theories ranked it as a motivator. In addition, Safiullah (2015) posits that an employee retaliates when they discover that there is lack of appreciation or the appreciation is too low relative to others in the same organisation. These dissatisfy employees.

There are several ways to recognize employees as individual or based on their achievements while at work (Hossain, 2012). Such recognition includes a greeting, acknowledging employee milestones, appreciating new ideas and holding celebrations for the success of the organisation. This can mean a lot to the employees' work and transforms the organisation environment.

However, employee recognition whether in cash or non-cash has a great impact on the organisation achievement of goals over the routine pay (Mikander, 2010). Supervisors and managers can also have an impact on employee motivation through the recognition of positive employee efforts and accomplishments. Recognition is an important aspect of keeping employees. Although it is a simple and cost-effective strategy but it is often overlooked as a viable solution to retention problems. According to Mikander (2010), non-cash recognitions tend to motivate the employees more because they are personalized based on ones achievement. Also, noncash recognition distinguishes the company reputation from others with its long and outstanding items that are rare and are imitable hence more individuals would prefer working in such reputable companies that value the works and achievements of their employees.

Motivation and Organizational Goal Achievement

Kelechi (2013) avers that motivation is one of the most important factors determining organization efficiency. All organisation resources get waste in the absence of motivated employees for proper use of the resources. In an organization, the main reason behind running activities is to achieve organizational goals. Organisation performance plays a principle role in attaining such goals. However, the performance of human beings in the organisation is dependent on the ability implanted in motivation. By providing proficiency and the employee connection to the organisation, motivation helps and thus improves performance in achieving organisation goals. Motivation is an effective instrument in inspiring the workforce to perform to achieve the organisation goals. Osabiya (2015) said motivation lead to high levels of job creativity at the workplace. It increases the willingness of the employees to work and ensure best efficient utilization of resources to achieve organisation goals. Employees should be motivated to carry out the plans, policies and programmes laid by the organisation (Kelechi, 2013). Organizational performance is all about attaining goals. Some believe it is simply how content an individual is with his or her job while some it is the willingness and the capacity to work to achieve the organisation goals. In other words, an employee can be physically and mentally fit to work but if he lacks motivation for the job and thus organisation goals cannot be achieved. Motivation bridges the gap between capacity to work and willingness to work. As a psychological catalyst according to Nabi (2017) motivation turns the spirit to embodied object. Organizational effectiveness is an extent up to which, the organization fulfills its goals using certain resources and with placing strain on its members. It also helps to ensure the operative use of human resource, gratification of employees, mutual consistency, durability of workforce which are important factors for attaining the organizational goals, smoothing organizational performance and thus bringing about job satisfaction (Nabi, 2017).

The Research Framework as illustrated in figure 1 is a conceptualization of the predictor of the achievement of organization goals. The achievement of organization goals is assumed to be determined as presented in the figure below:

Source: Adapted from Herzberg, 1957.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Robbins (2010) states that, according to Herzberg theory, intrinsic factors such as career advancement, recognition, responsibility and achievement relates to job satisfaction. These intrinsic factors relate to job context because they are much concerned with what an employee does at work that enhances or reduces productivity and commitment (Mullins, 2005).

Further, Gellerman (1963) states that the presence of the intrinsic factors is to motivate employees to superior work effort and work performance. This is affirmed by Mullins (2005). However, their absence does not cause any particular dissatisfaction in the employees; it just fails to motivate (Mullins, 2005). These motivator factors include self actualisation, self-esteem and social needs of Abraham Maslow's hierarchy. When an employee's social needs are met and they have achieved something important in life, they feel good, satisfied and motivated.

METHODOLOGY

The Research Design; This study adopted a causal type research design of study to examine the effect of intrinsic motivation factors on the achievement of organisational goals at Malawi Adventist University.

The Population and Sampling Procedure: The target population consisted of 241 permanent and contract employees. From this population, 181 employees were randomly selected as the sample for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection: Investigators- structured questionnaire titled “Employees Intrinsic Motivation and the Attainment of Organisational Goals Questionnaire” with Likert scaling method of five point intervals ranging from 5=Strongly Agree 4= Agree 3= Neither Agree or Disagree 2= Disagree 1= Strongly Disagree was used to collect data from the responses. Section A described the demography of the employees such as age, gender, education qualification, job position, years of service and job status. Section B had close ended questions on the variables under study –with 16 question on employees Intrinsic motivations and 6 question on organizational goals. While section C had open ended questions where the respondents had the opportunity to express their views in writing with items on the scale.

Method of Data Analysis: Frequency tables were employed to analyse the demography of the respondents as well as the descriptive factors of motivation. Inferential statistics deemed appropriate for the study such that correlation and multiple regression analyses were used to answer the research question and the null hypothesis of the study with the use of SPSS statistical package version 22.

DATA PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Out of the 181 copies of questionnaire distributed to the respondents, 155 were returned representing 85.6% retrieval rate. 9 questionnaires were not duly completed, thus, discarded leaving the 146 questionnaires as duly completed. Thus, the result presented was based on the 146 copies of the questionnaire that were duly completed representing 80.6% response rate.

Table 1. Distribution by Employee Job Category

Job Category	Frequency	Percent
Permanent	112	76.7
Contract	34	23.3
Total	146	100.0

(Source: Field Data, 2018)

Table 1 above indicate that 112 respondents were permanent workers representing 76.7% while 34 contract workers representing 23.3%. Based on these results, it can be

concluded that the majority of the respondents were permanent workers. This indicates that most of Malawi Adventist University employees are on permanent basis.

Table 2. Distribution by Employee Job Status

Job Status	Frequency	Percent
Teaching	49	33.6
Non Teaching	97	66.4
Total	146	100.0

(Source: Field Data, 2018)

Table 2 above shows the employee job status of the 146 respondents under study, 97 were non-teaching staff representing 66.4% and 49 of the respondents were teaching staff representing 33.6%. This means that majority of employee at the Malawi Adventist University are non-teaching staff.

Research Question: *To what extent does intrinsic motivation factors affect the achievement of organisation goals at Malawi Adventist University?*

In order to address the research question, the researchers used descriptive statistics to find the intrinsic motivation factors that are important to Malawi Adventist University employees. The degree of agreement of the respondents is based on the 5 point Likert response scale. The expected mean for very important factor is 5 and the analysis is based on how the mean responses of the respondents are close to the expected. Table 3 below shows the descriptive responses and interpretation for each of the mean scores.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics- Intrinsic Motivation Factors important to employees

Intrinsic factors	Mean	Standard deviation	Interpretation
Work life Balance	3.81	.80	Important
Nature of work	4.00	.80	Important
Employee Wellbeing	3.31	1.08	Not sure
Equity and fairness	3.59	1.01	Important
Responsibility	4.04	.71	Important
Recognition	3.66	.85	Important

(Source: Field Data, 2018)

Legend: Interval scale of 1.00-1.49 = Not important at all, 1.50-2.49 = Not important, 2.50-3.49 = Not Sure, 3.50-4.49 = Important and 4.50-5.00 = Very important.

Table 3 results indicated the highest mean score on employee responsibility of $M=4.04$, $SD=.71$, followed by nature of work ($M=4.00$, $SD=.80$), work life balance ($M=3.81$, $SD=.80$), employee recognition ($M=3.66$, $SD=.85$), equity and fairness ($M=3.59$, $SD=1.01$) while employee well being had the least mean score of 3.31 , $SD=1.08$ indicated that employees were not sure if the factor was important. Their standard deviation ranged from $.71-1.08$ measured the degree to which the scores in the distribution deviated from the means.

As stated in literature, not all motivation factors are equally important to employees at the same time. Some factors are more important than others such that they provide much more powerful drive to an employee to work and achieve organisation goals (Robbins, 2010 and Armstrong, 2006). As shown in table 3 above, the mean scores of the intrinsic motivation factors ranged between a high of 4.04 and a low of 3.59 indicated that respondents agreed to the fact that motivation factors are not the same for all employees. The results revealed that responsibility, nature of work, work life balance, employee recognition, equity and fairness are the intrinsic motivation factors important to employees in achieving the organisation goals as evidenced by their mean scores.

Research Hypothesis: *Employees' intrinsic motivation factors does not significantly affect the achievement of organisation goals at Malawi Adventist University.*

In general, to examine the extent at which the intrinsic motivation factors affected the achievement of organisation goals at Malawi Adventist University, correlation matrix was computed to assess the relationship. Table 4 below presents the results.

Table 4. Relationship - Intrinsic Motivation Factors and the Achievement of Organisation Goals

Intrinsic motivation factors	Organisation goals	
Work life balance	Pearson Correlation	.124
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.136
Nature of work	Pearson Correlation	.308**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
Wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.089
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.283
Equity and fairness	Pearson Correlation	.150
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.071

Responsibility	Pearson Correlation	.320**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
Recognition	Pearson Correlation	.240**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004

(Source: Field Data, 2018) N=146

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results in Table 4 above present the relationship between intrinsic motivation factors and the achievement of organisation goals. It shows significant positive relationships between intrinsic motivation factors and the achievement of organisation goals on these factors: nature of work ($r = .308^{**}$, $p < .05$), responsibility ($r = .320^{**}$, $p < .05$) and recognition ($r = .240^{**}$, $p < .05$). These results therefore indicate a significant relationship between the intrinsic motivation factors and the achievement of organisation goals. On the contrary the results also indicated that there is no relationship on factors like work life balance, well being, equity and fairness.

To further determine the effect of the intrinsic motivation factors multiple regression analysis was conducted. Table 5 presents the results below.

Table 5. Multiple Regression- Intrinsic Motivation Factors and the Achievement of Organisation Goals

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
	(Constant)	3.083	.290			
1	Work life Balance	-.020	.055	-.032	-.363	.717
	Nature of work	.113	.057	.180	1.961	.052
	Wellbeing	-.011	.040	-.024	-.280	.780
	Equity and fairness	.019	.041	.039	.464	.643
	Responsibility	.158	.061	.225	2.574	.011
	Recognition	.080	.050	.136	1.593	.113

(Source: Field Data, 2018)

a. Dependent Variable: Organisation goals

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.400 ^a	.160	.123	.47048

(Source: Field Data, 2018)

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Recognition, equity and fairness, responsibility, well being, work life balance and nature of work

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.850	6	.975	4.405	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.768	139	.221		
	Total	36.618	145			

(Source: Field Data, 2018)

- a. Dependent Variable: Organisation goals
 a. Predictors: (Constant), Recognition, responsibility, nature of work, well being, work life balance, equity and fairness.

The results in table 5 shows an F value of 4.405 with a corresponding p- value < 0.05 indicating a significant effect between the intrinsic motivation factors and the achievement of organisation goals. A critical look at table 5 reveals that nature of work with (Beta) of .180, t=1.961 and p < 0.05 and employee responsibility with (Beta) of .225, t= 2.574 and p < 0.05, explains the significant degrees of variation in the achievement of organisation goals. More so, the adjusted R square of .123 means that approximately 12% of the total variation in organisation goal achievement is as a result of the nature of work and employee responsibility. The multiple coefficient of the regression Multiple R, of .400^a also indicates a strong correlation.

These results seem to collaborate with Riley (2005) that entrusting employees with responsibility in different positions contribute to the achievement of organisation goals. This will encourage employees to work hard and prove that their work contributions mean a lot for the success of their organisations. The success of the organisation is dependent on the employee's nature of work and a sense of responsibility. Creating a sense of responsibility indicates that managers trust and have confidence in employees that they will carry out work properly without close supervision. Besides, a confident employee works beyond manager's expectation due to the excitement and the trusted work (Lavinsky, 2012). They are responsible and motivated hence they own the challenges and the success of the organisation. This therefore suggests that if managers' entrust employees with responsibility they will intrinsically get motivated and eventually the organisation is likely to benefit more.

Furthermore, these results seem to agree with Colquitt (2013) suggestion that employees work hard when they enjoy their work. The enjoyment comes due to the nature of work the employee is involved in and this provides job satisfaction. Employees who are satisfied appreciate their jobs and work passionately to fulfil their job demands without being pushed. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims that intrinsic motivation factors does not significantly affect the achievement of the organisation goals is rejected.

On the other hand, since the other intrinsic motivation factors such as work life balance, recognition, wellbeing, equity and fairness did not prove as significant in the regression matrix, the null hypothesis is accepted.

CONCLUSION

Employee motivation is a very important subject that managers need to consider when dealing with human resource to effectively achieve organisation goals. The study dealt with some of Herzberg (1957) intrinsic motivator and satisfier factors such as work life balance, nature of work, wellbeing, equity and fairness, responsibility and recognition at Malawi Adventist University. Based on the findings of this study, intrinsic employee motivation affects the achievement of organization goal at Malawi Adventist University. Further, the findings revealed that all intrinsic motivation factors except for one that was not certain are important (though not equally) to employees in achieving the organisation goals. Moreover, there is a significant positive relationship between nature of work, responsibility, recognition, and achievement of organisation goals. Thus, these factors are the predictors of organisation goal achievement.

However, there is more room for improvement in the way employees are intrinsically motivated in achieving organization goal at Malawi Adventist University. Thus this recommendation:

Management must ensure proper supervision and monitoring of the subordinates to track the progress of the work and be able to spot the challenges faced by the employees as they carry out their day to day operations. This will enable them express their challenges and how management can overcome those challenges to achieve the organisation goals.

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